

Quality improvement project proposal

FACILITY: CHUK

Title of the project: Evaluation of feeding of critically ill patients

Problem statement:

Critically ill patients in the A&E department at CHUK are often fed by next of kin, who have limited knowledge of how to feed correctly and safely or which foods to give. These patients often become malnourished, faulted to poor feeding and consequential prolonged hospital stay. And co morbidities/complications developed quickly in these patients like pressure sore, malnutrition, hospital acquired infection and poor outcome.

Data are showing that optimal nutrition therapy is essential to improve the long-term outcome to reduce the likelihood of the patient to becoming a victim of critical illness(1) And current evidence found that critically ill patients are in hyper catabolic state requiring timely and adequate nutrition support and later promoting the host immunity and hence minimizing nutritionally related complications while improving overall outcome(2)(3). Different barriers have been found to hamper nutrition of critically ill patients. These barriers are (1) other aspects of patient care taking priority over nutrition, (2) not enough feeding pumps available, (3) enteral formula not available on the unit, (4) difficulties in obtaining small bowel access in patients not tolerating enteral nutrition, and (5) no or not enough dietitian coverage during weekends and holidays(4). And a recent study done in Kenya assessing nursing enteral nutrition practices and perspectives in ICU at level6 hospital showed nurses' fair awareness of nutritional practices and perspectives despites some gaps in the field.(5)

Patient needs regular feeding like he needs other treatment according to his/her illness. And it is important to note that enteral feeding may serve therapeutic role providing calories and proteins. But feeding itself becomes a problem and yield more devastating complications when it is not done regularly by professionals (nurses) and with adequate quality and quantity of balanced diet. And this could have negative effect to the patient and poor prognosis of at the end(3).

By developing patient centered care services, we would also focus on improvement of patient timely enteral feeding with balanced diet in quality and quantity and making feeding done as prescription, administered and documented like other medication by health professional instead of next of kin.

Current patient feeding situation is not patient centered, leading to patients' malnutrition and poor outcome (undesirable event).

Goal statement: Efficient feeding critically ill patients

Project to be done by: Resident Faustin TURAMYIMANA,

Plan:

To determine if there is or no system issue in feeding patients
To report findings data to department of A&E administration.

Responsible of the project: PGYII Faustin TURAMYIMANA

Supervisor: Dr TWAGIRUMUKIZA Francois Regis

Patients are indirectly included by evaluating efficiency of their nutrition

The project will be done by checking patient's files once a week for four weeks (from 25/07-21/08/2022)

Do:

Change to be made to improve patient feeding

1. Feeding of critically ill patients is priority like other medications and it should be prescribed in precise dose and administered like other medications/actions
2. Feeding should appear or have its column on prescription sheet
3. Food administration should be done by professionals not next of kin and should be documented
4. Feeding should be done in appropriate quality and quantity in terms of calories, proteins, minerals, carbohydrates

Reevaluation of above mentioned goals will be done one month two month after presentation of data to A & E department administration

Implementation will be done by physician and nurse team including nutritionist, for patients in room 8 and 9 respectively, at CHUK A&E Dept. (Physicians and Matron would check on daily basis on implementation of the recommendation).

Changes will be done as soon as possible and reevaluation two months later

Later administration would focus on staff understanding on importance of feeding patients, clinical implication

Evaluation and sources of data

By data collection, we will review how (route), when, what (quality and quantity), administered by whom, documented feeding, and all those data will be gathered from patient file

Data will be reviewed by supervisor, quality improvement team after submission date

Data will be reviewed, compiled and presented by TURAMYIMANA Faustin

3. Btaiche IF, Chan LN, Pleva M, Kraft MD. Critical Illness, gastrointestinal complications, and medication therapy during enteral feeding in critically ill adult patients. *Nutr Clin Pract*. 2010;25(1):32–49.
4. Cahill NE, Murch L, Cook D, Heyland DK. Barriers to feeding critically ill patients: A multicenter survey of critical care nurses. *J Crit Care* [Internet]. 2012;27(6):727–34. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrc.2012.07.006>
5. KOMEN D. Assessing Nursing Enteral Nutrition Practices and Perspectives in An Intensive Care Unit of A Level Six Hospital in Kenya. *Asian J Pharmacy, Nurs Med Sci*. 2020;8(6):84–91.